

Effectiveness of Service Delivery System in Public Service

NzenwataChisom Beauty

P.M.B 174 Garki, G.P.O Abuja

Abstract:-Despite the continuous reforms and increase in demands for socio-economic and developmental services in Nigeria, sadly, deficient service delivery has constantly bedeviled the growth of the entire country. National Orientation Agency and other sister organizations for now, have not done enough in orientating the citizens on how to be selfless in service delivery. In promoting effective service delivery, the Nigerian government needs to focus on reshaping, rebuilding the mentality of those that are in positions of delivering services to the people. The findings of this study links factors such as lack of proper orientation, poor training, ineffective communication channels, attitudes of workers, corruption. The study applied secondary method of data collection to analyze the effect of poor service delivery in the development of Nigeria;it outlined the implications associated with a failed service delivery system.Further the studyrecommended strategies; strict adherence and implementation of this will improve service delivery, thereby, reducing more likelihood of failure.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Service Delivery System, Public Service, Orientation, Mindset

I. INTRODUCTION

Effective service delivery has a specific goal in mind - to meet with expectations of an end-product user. Though, product may be termed more of a tangible or physical object, however, it also includes services. A direct interface of service providing, is the relationship between a service rendering organization and consumers, the objective is to create a satisfactory relationship thereby meeting expectations. According to Grönroos and Ravald (2011) high quality services delivery is a vital pursuit for service providers that aim to create and provide value to their

respective customers. In the daily lives of many, people go out in search of services they need. Agba et al.(2013) opined that one of the ways of bringing government closer to the people at the grassroots is through effective service delivery in a satisfactory, efficient, effective and adequate manner. Leni et al. (2012) despite several plans and massive injections of international and domestic resources to improve service delivery system; public service delivery is still failing in many developing countries.

The Nigerian public service may well be known for its poor service delivery system, most local government workers and in fact, the public servants have been described as inhibiting poor work attitude detrimental to productivity. Akerele, 1986; Odiaka, 1991; Ogunrin and Erhijakpor, 2009 pointed out poor work attitude in form of absenteeism, indiscipline, laziness, lack of work commitment, lateness to work. Aremu and Babarinde(2010) opined that the poor attitude of workers which is mostly experienced in the public sector has negatively affected customers' satisfaction and economic development of the country.

This was one of the reasons that led to the launch of a delivery service initiative service compact(**SERVICOM**) was signed by former Nigerian President Olusegun Obasanjo, over a decade ago. It was meant to improve citizen satisfaction by promoting effective service delivery system in the public service. Ogunrin & Erhijakpor (2009) believes that **SERVICOM** policy is meant to be sustained, alongside other related initiatives, until Nigerian public life is truly transformed.

However, since this initiative was launch, there has been little or no improvement, as would have been expected. King 1988 observed that Nigerians have been well aware of the unpleasant manifestation of the appalling standards of

service delivery in the country, under the popular caption of 'the Nigerian way'. He further opined that many Nigerians have grown accustomed to the fact that public service is something to battle for and may not succeed unless an individual has a connection to the system.

This may be as a result of failure to work on the Nigerian mentality first before launching an initiative for a particular purpose. The Nigerian Orientation Agency (NOA) which is one of the most important agencies in Nigeria may not be doing enough when it comes to orientation. Further he states that, most observers would agree that civic education, political education as well as putting out the appropriate information are necessary components in driving appropriate citizens' participation in the political process. Unfortunately, knowledge of all these are limited in the Nigerian polity due to the near incapacity of the NOA.

Educating the citizens for effective service delivery in the public service should begin with the mentality. Working on the mentality of those that relate or liaise directly with consumers or end-product users is massively important.

The reason service delivery system in Nigerian public service may be poor as witnessed in public service may be because; some individuals do not know how to prioritize collective interest before personal. Collective interests help everyone to grow, including a service deliverer; it leaves the public service, consumers, even the society as a whole healthy. Good service is to be benefitted by everyone if shared interest and cooperation is involved.

The purpose of this article is to examine the service delivery system in Nigeria and infuse into the public servants the mentality of the importance of serving humanity and not for humanity to be at the mercy of the society. The specific objectives are to: examine the service delivery systems impact on public service productivity as a whole. Enumerate the present state of Nigeria working environment for a better understanding. Identify and explain the causes of poor service delivery systems in Nigeria. Suggest solutions or the way forward to improve and sustain service delivery systems.

Against this background, the study is structured into four parts. Part one examines the introduction, background of service delivery system. Part two examines the empirical review of literature on previous researches. Part three examines the research questions, methodology, analysis and explanations of the findings. Part four recommends the way forward and conclusion.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This work is designed as one of the measures geared towards stalling ineffectiveness in service delivery in the Nigerian working environment. It evaluates how detrimental lack of consciousness for service delivery has negatively affected the progress of the Nigerian working environment including the country's economy. According to Walley and Amin (1994) service delivery systems is expected to produce several positive outcomes, ranging from reduced costs, increased availability of efficient operations, improved service quality and optimum customer experience. Badmus B.G (2017) opined that public service delivery is very paramount to the government and citizens of any country; hence the need for effective service delivery to meet the demands of citizens can never be exaggerated. Eigeman (2007), states that the level of citizen satisfaction in service offered by the government is an important factor in the acceptance of any government; he further opined that the key element that shape the relationship between elected representatives and voters is trust. Parasuraman et al. (1988) defined service quality as the extent to which an organization meets or exceed expectations of customers. Zeithaml et al. (1990) defined service delivery as the gap between customer expectations of service and how they perceived the service. They further explained perceived service quality as derivation from comparisons by customers of expectations with what they perceive of service delivery by the service deliverer. Author Bitner (1994) states that customers' expectations are according to their perceptions of service that serve as quality against which service delivered is judged.

Parasuraman et al., (1988) states that expectations are what beneficiaries think a service should deliver rather than what might be the offered. Lovelock, 1984; Armistead, 1990 opined that the main aim of a service delivery system is to

bridge the gap between customer expectations and customer experience. A large number of studies reveal that the effectiveness of the service delivery system affects customers' perceptions of the quality of service they received. e.g. Hensel, 1990; Kingman-Brundage, 1991.

Correspondingly, some studies also demonstrated using empirical research, the positive influence of specific variables of service delivery on perceived service quality such as Hartline and Ferrel, 1996, Parasuraman et al. 1988. Other researchers like Mandell, 1991, Haynes and DuVall, 1992 either measured specific outputs of the system, such as time required for task execution, costs, etc. while Ponsignon, Smart & Maull, 2011, use proxy variables and assess the effectiveness of its most important determinants.

Scotland police service was studied by Donnelly et al. (2006) the aim was to examine the support of the service internal process provisions and the understanding of their customers' expectations. Service quality (SERVQUAL) technique was applied and it revealed that the police have a good understanding of their customer's expectation. From the customers' perspective it revealed the need to improve in quality service and compliance to quality standard. Wisniewski (2001) studied on customer satisfaction using Scottish councils' public sector, it shows that customers' expectations were not met; there was noticeable negative gaps between dimensions of tangibles and reliability. Ramseok-Munhurrum et al. (2010) applied SERVQUAL model to Mauritius public sector to examine the extent to which customer expectations of service delivered match the front-line employees' perceptions of customer expectations. The study shows a noticeable gap in meeting customer expectations, it also pointed out that front-line employees' have an idea of what the customers expect.

Further, Anderson (1995) applied the five dimensions of the SERVQUAL model to investigate the quality of service delivered by the public health clinic of the University of Houston Health Centre, the result shows that patients have a high level of dissatisfaction under assurance, hence empathy and tangibles shows the lowest level. In other words total level of service delivered by the health care was dissatisfactory and never met the expectations of beneficiaries.

Nevertheless, we observed that very few studies described variables and assessed the general impact of service delivery system effectiveness on service quality, through the direct influence of the individual service delivery variables. Some studies opined that the governments of most countries are to be blamed while others such as Hartline and Ferrell, 1996; Bettencourt and Brown, 1997 based their studies on service delivery variables. But one thing was missing, mentality; they never focused on the mindset and orientation which is the ultimate in effective service delivery system. Specifically, this study argues that the most important determinants of effective service delivery systems are the front line employees' whose mindset needs to be structured.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted qualitative research design which involves historical analysis and review of relevant literature, public service reforms, textbooks, journal articles, newspapers and the Internet. The content analysis technique was adopted to provide an in-depth assessment of the main force that has curtailed a speedy improvement of service delivery, despite the abundance of human and material resources at the country's disposal. Thematic and secondary data analysis techniques were applied to answer and explain the research questions; it also enumerated the implications associated with a failed service delivery system, also bringing out measures that would see to its improvements, thereby, reducing more likelihood of failure.

❖ RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study is motivated by four research questions.

How does effective service delivery system impact public service productivity?

What is the present state of Nigerian working environment and its impact on effective service delivery?

What is the relationship with mindset and service effectiveness?

What are the causes of failed service delivery system in public service of Nigeria?

➤ *Analysis and discussion*

RQ1: How does effective service delivery system impact

public service productivity?

➤ *An overview of Service Delivery*

An ideal way to distinguish a business from probable competitors is to foster strong customer relationships; quality of service sets a business apart from its rivals. Services are resources including time, tools, equipment's, staff, management, planning, performance, put together to bridge the gap between customer expectations and the expected delivery. Delivery is the final process of these resources that were put together to meeting the expectations of a customer or the public. Druker, (2004) states that system effectiveness is described as the capability of producing a specific, desired effect, or "getting the right things done". According to Goldstein et al. 2002 service delivery system is defined as "the structure (facilities, equipment, etc.), infrastructure (job design, skills, etc.) and processes for delivering a service". Reasonably, the most important of an effective service delivery system are the front line employees, their roles, performances, ability to adapt to individual or group customers. They reflect the most important outcome of a service delivery network and that capacity to satisfy customer/public needs and creating a value. Kingman-Brundage, (1991) opined that service delivery system effectiveness is closely related to the level to which a system's goal have been achieved and therefore, an effective service delivery system is the one that is capable of delivering the outcome for which it was originally designed and developed. Walley and Amin, (1994) argues that Service delivery systems normally should produce several positive outcomes, ranging from reduced costs, and increased availability of efficient operations, improved service quality and optimum customer experience. Public service employers needs to engage its frontline employees to deliver the ultimate customer value, of course, the trend today is that everyone working for an organization is a frontline employee.

Therefore excellent service delivery enhances peace between a service renderer and the public or a consumer; it creates a serene environment for growth, as well as securing and strengthening public and private institutions. In a drive for good service delivery and as a service deliverer, a business need to ensure that it's on same thinking with its customers, regarding expectations of what it has to deliver,

expectations like cost of service, limitations (if any) and how good the service will turn out. Customers feel more comfortable when they are kept abreast of what is going on.

In other words, effective service delivery comes with the knowledge of co-creation, which means that prospective customers are part of the creation or production of goods and services, that's the premise in which product or service chain are built.

➤ *Service delivery as a spring board*

It will be difficult for one to undermine the importance of effective service(s), its more than making sales. It includes, managing consumer satisfaction, thereby, commanding loyalty which is an essential strategy for a successful profit making organization. Therefore, effective service delivery launches a business to the driving seat in a competitive environment; it earns the trust of the public. It becomes a springboard to becoming a trademark for others to follow or a benchmark for emulation; it becomes a step to maximizing increase revenue. Effective service delivery keeps customers glued to an organization's services/products. Getting people in is key; however, making them stay could be a challenge. Customers who come back for more services/products are those whose chances of being kept are highly likely. So, that should be an area of stronghold. Through the provision of high levels of service quality, companies can achieve increased customer satisfaction, loyalty and therefore long-term profitability Zeithaml and Bitner, (2000) Quality service delivery is a springboard for an enhanced reputation of an organization, consumers never forget the type of services rendered to them by a service deliverer and as such, they tend to talk about their experiences when dealing with others, even close relatives. It may become severe when such services were really poor or not up to standards. It's very important to note that when satisfied consumers refer others to the services of an organization, it builds the organization's customer base. When a sizable consumer base has been built, it increases sales, thereby increase in profit which automatically improve developmental process of a country.

➤ *Service delivery, a key to productivity*

Effective service delivery plays a very vital role in the productivity of employees, when a mind has been

conditioned to go an extra mile in making customers feel valued; it leads to a greater amount of productivity. Below are some of the important factors that need to key in to ensure an improved service delivery.

Training: Public service employees who interface directly or indirectly with customers are given orientation on how to handle customers complaints, trained in product knowledge, equipped mentally in the operations of the internal and external systems of a service delivering organization, it provides incentives for an improved productivity. In this regard, employees are motivated to work harder, more skillfully. It improves their behavior, skills, knowledge and attitude towards an effective service delivery and performance. Training should be a continuous process for a workforce associated with a private or public organization; this will help public service employees to be at speed with business and working trends.

Technology: Added use of technology is another way to ensuring an excellent service delivery system, the right technology tends to make a workforce more productive, more innovative and more efficient towards consumers. In tasks that may require huge amount of time, can be completed within a shorter time frame through the aid of technology. Technology affords employees to have jobs done from anywhere; you must not necessarily be stationed in a particular office or to a stationed computer device. This affords one the luxury to attend to customers instantly without having to be stationed at the office, employee can work remotely. It encourages speed in attending to some of the impromptu needs of customers. For instance, making use of Wi-Fi or internet service enables employees to work from wherever they are that will be most comfortable with them in reaching out effectively to customers, it improves productivity. This works perfectly when employers encourage the use of Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) for their employees.

Motivation: The best is given under the guidance of an individual who possesses good management skills, someone that knows how to psyche up people's abilities, help them utilize their capabilities, making them want to go extra step in getting a job done to exceed expectations, convincing them to love what they do with passion. The real job of a

manager is helping employees realize their hidden potentials; saddled with the responsibility to get employee out from their comfort zone. Note that this is outside financial incentives as peculiar with most Nigerian minds who do not get motivated without money. For clearer understanding, public service employees must be put in a healthy state of living for them to work smarter and better, which in turn, boost service delivery and productivity level. That is to say that a business needs its employees for growth more than the employees need the business. Motivation is a force that influences one to do things differently. Employer motivates public service employee by ensuring they are in a healthy state, mentally, emotionally, esteemed, financially and physically. When services are delivered by a motivated group, it rubs off on customers as magic happens they give their all, it's psychological. A motivated public servant comes with good service delivery; they work with high press, a different flow of energy. A healthy and happy service deliverer is willing to invest their physical and mental resources in what they do for their employer, to the benefit of customers.

Societal orientation: It may well be said that an enhanced productivity of public service organizations is one the functions of employees' contribution, added with the required orientation for more excellent service delivery. It is one thing to employ, yet, greater emphasis should be laid on orientation. A newly employed may be eager to start work, however, the right orientation guides on how to go about duties and responsibilities. The importance of societal orientation has been hugely neglected in Nigeria; this is where the role of NOA is greatly needed. From observations, one may have noticed that most employments in the country are done just for the sake of giving out jobs to some that have been persisting their godfathers, uncles, aunties, etc, without an efforts to know if they are well baked to fit into the society. The importance of societal orientation is to the benefit of the society. Societal orientation leads to uniformed processes throughout the whole nation, greater sense of responsibility is added. The masses both the service deliverer and service seeker becomes more productive, having sense of responsibility.

RQ2: What is the present state of Nigerian working environment?

➤ *Present state of the Nigerian working environment*

How a community utilizes its environment determines how well it grows. Man's immediate environment is his first point of call in his everyday pursuit of growth. Some tend to utilize it with the right approach, while others fail so awkwardly, this may be attributed to lack of a good mindset. Improper utilization of an environment creates room for underdevelopment, when an environment is not favorable or friendly, it does not allow for proper discharge of services to intended customers. A type of environment tells how well it can function, when the environment is toxic, hardly would better services emanate from there. In relation to the Nigerian working environment, it has gone so deplorable that most persons sometimes, look reluctant to attend to issues when money is not involved. Lewis and Alemika (2005) study observed that Nigerians are deeply dissatisfied with the performance of democracy and had no trust in the country's major institutions. Adamolekun, (1986) opined that the Nigerian civil service always encounters criticism for poor organization, laziness, truancy, malingering, indiscipline insensitivity, incompetence, corruption and favoritism. etc.

According to the former president of Nigeria Obasanjo, (2007) the pursuance of government contracts has become the priority of public officers. Citizens are at the receiving end of whatever comes out of the poor services, He further stated that, public servants receive bribe in order to deliver a service and often times files get lost on transit without any trace. He blamed the service delivery officers; they have demonstrated high level of inefficiency and corruption to the detriment of prompt and efficient implementation of governmental policies in Nigeria. One may notice that upon visiting some Nigerian working places, especially government owned organizations, most employees attend to an inquiry or need of a client or consumer with expectations of something in return (appreciation). Showing appreciation to a service deliverer is not bad, but, when it is a priority to attending to clients, it becomes unacceptable. Gboyega, (1996) the Nigerian public service has degenerated into the present circumstances of poor service delivery when public servants, if they serve you at all, do so as a favor or at a price. Is unfortunate how negligent some public servant will leave a consumer or client, to his fate, once they observe

that they are likely to get nothing in return. The Nigerian government that blindly make reforms or establish bodies they feel will improve service delivery, is hugely to be blamed for this. If a government makes reforms or creates establishments, who are to manage them? Sadly, the same individuals whose mindsets are corrupt. The Nigerian mind has been so corrupt that almost everyone is selfish, thinking for personal interest and not the society, selfish mindset can never deliver an excellent service. Political leaders do not seem to take responsibility for this problem as everyone is blaming others. Those in government have succeeded in making employees directly or indirectly understand that individuals need to work for the money, not the community. They crave for money, at the expense of the economic growth of the country. Some of these political or appointed leaders hate being held accountable for this deplorable thinking of most Nigerian employees. What may be ruining Nigeria's economic growth is collective selfishness. This endemic problem that is orchestrated by those at the helm of governance, descending to those picking up peanuts thrown to them by these inconsiderate elites, is gradually destroying the future of the nation.

This makes those at the near bottom to follow suit by indulging in any act, whether legitimate or illegitimate, moral or immoral, ethical or unethical that will see to their survival, this is the reason the Nigerian state/working environment is and may remain in chaos if the mentality is not reset. Often times some security men at a post expect exchange from a visitor in order to render services effectively. Agreed, some workers may not be well paid to cater for essential family needs, greedy and inconsiderate bosses are to be blamed. This has led to the popular parlance, "na Nigeria we dey", it has become a mental challenge to those that practice it. This is a huge challenge facing the development of the Nigerian state. It appears to be deep-rooted in the mind-sets of many, the leaders and masses. The state of our mindset needs to be hugely improved on because; it is what affects our daily acts and relating with the society. There should be a shift in our present mindset to more collective ways of operating. It is obvious that what led the Nigerian mindset to this level is corruption and negligence, because it was never like this in the 70s and 80s of the 19th century. Why has the Nigerian mentality become this way? Why has it become part of our

daily routines? The leaders act like they are unaware of what is happening or how to arrest the situation. Nigeria is blessed with abundance of human and material resources at its disposal, yet, the lack of a good mindset on the part of the employee, including those on every echelon of administration, has been a thorn towards maximum utilization of these resources. Different ills can be associated with a society largely made up of ineffective, not well equipped mindset, but the champion of it all is poor service delivery system. Others include rising unemployment, higher level of poverty, slow pace of growth and development in the society's economy. The Nigerian authorities should get the mentality of Nigerians sorted already before thinking of reforms needed to improve good service delivery in the country. It is said that where minds are corrupt, positivity is dead.

RQ3: What is the relationship with mindset and service effectiveness?

➤ *Service effectiveness begins with the mindset*

The steady consciousness of loving and respecting mankind is one of the inhibitors that shape a human mind towards being effective. Irrespective of differences in backgrounds, ideological beliefs, races, religion, creed, humanity is just a family. Sharing this thought is acknowledging that humans are different beings tied to the same root (mankind), it calls for respect and love for one another. This how best the mind should be shaped when attending to people, strive to see the next person look happy, strive to see the look of satisfaction in people, strive to see humans feel loved. There are few service providers that care to see service seekers happy, that is an excellent mind. Learning how to interact with an environment makes the relationship get better and also brings perfection. The mind is originally built on a clean slate and the choice of what is filled with tells the personality of someone. A master of the mind manages an environment effectively; it is in control of it. Negative thoughts, affects an environment negatively to the detriment of an individual and the society at large. Consequently what occupies a public service deliverer's mindset is what is displayed on the outside. Not being a master of the mind entails risk of being ruled by external forces. It is important to note that a clear idea of making the world a better place to live in should be one of the first lines

of thought for every public service employee. Becoming a better service provider needs embracing the spirit of learning new positives, the mind can accommodate beyond comprehension. Continuous learning brings one into new worlds outside what has been known already. The mind can be trained to think positively of people, rid off negative thoughts like being selfish and greedy, sentimental, biased and unethical. In other words, the relationship between mindset and effectiveness can never be overemphasis as they work hand in hand, when a mindset is built positively it delivers effective results.

RQ4: What are the causes of failed service delivery system in public service of Nigeria?

➤ *Causes of a failed service delivery system in the country*

There is more to leadership than ordering people around, expecting positive results. It is not mere having a workforce under your control; it is chiefly building the minds of a workforce to excel in quality service delivery. Ways through which a failed service delivery system emanates from include the following but not limited to:

Lack of Orientation: In general, where there is failure in meeting up with expectations, it is obvious that there is a loop hole in the orientation of the service providers. The most important gift to a newly employed is giving an indebt orientation of how the job is done, the environment, how to relate with the public on behalf of the employer. All these boils down to how well the mindset has been baked through orientation. Lack of orientation gives birth to poor service delivery. According to Management Study HQ, 'orientation which is called Induction is designed to provide a new employee with the information he or she needs to function comfortably and effectively in the organization'. Effective orientation programmes reduce the anxiety of new employees by providing them with information on the job, the environment or its scope. Orientation is a fundamental mental function that processes the relations between the behaving self to place, time, and persons. It works with the mind and responds to spaces, events and people. It is how shaped it is that determines how responsive it will be to its environment, what is deposited is what it brings out to the society.

Lack/poor Training: Other causes of a failed service delivery system are rooted or linked with lack or poor training. Training is an activity done on regular basis; it should be a constant activity in a work place. Orientation is totally different from training and it has been observed that Nigerian employers has fall short of this act. It is record that 80% of Nigerian public service employees never goes for training after their first orientation, as this has cause poor service delivery. Most employees that undergo training sometimes get diluted quality which cannot help them to deliver effectively. In this technology age, trends keep changing so should service providers be trained and updated with the latest in other to deliver services effectively. Hence an organization's business is on daily routine; training should be an ongoing practice to put excellent service delivery built into their respective mindset. To build a credible customer base, employees must be knowledgeable, not just on how to deliver friendly and helpful services, but how to relate with customer enquiries. Having knowledge creates confidence, builds public credibility and improves one's charismatic qualities.

Lack of customers as priority: Customers as priority should be the first aim of every business, when customers have the feeling that an organization is slow in responding to their enquiries or complaints, or a lackadaisical attitude been shown towards their concern, it may give them the impression that their needs are not valued. Speed of service is one of the core principles to be inculcated, especially when a customer requests something that is time sensitive. Acting on the needs of customers leaves them with a feel-good factor; it makes them feel belonged and appreciated. Hence, customers should be carried along, if a service provider cannot attend to their anticipation urgently, it will be worthwhile to relate with them on how best to resolve their issues at a later date. When not resolving issues urgently, Is really discouraging when customers are been put on hold far too long than necessary,.

Poor communication channel: Poor communication channel is one of the causes of poor service delivery by the public service. Most times organization communication channels may not be active, but they never update their contact or communicate to their customers, example live chats, social media, websites etc. These are the easiest

channel to communicate to service providers; unfortunately response rate is very poor because the channels are inactive. When customers are given the support they needed, they trust and appreciate organization's brand and which leads to improved patronage. How easy for them to contact a service provider by including clear information that like e-mail address, phone number(s), live chats and other media channels, this makes it an easier task in responding to their complaints. Is worthwhile for public service providers to adapt to the technology changes of making use of their online service to deliver better support.

Corruption: Corruption in Nigeria is a huge research topic on its own because is a widespread and endemic in Nigeria. Is one of Nigeria's biggest problem which has gave birth to poor service delivery and also known as the father of underdevelopment. Scholars in the past recommended that anti-corruption battle must be monitored by legislative framework for transparent and accountable government; leaders must have the political will and commitment to fight corruption, that a systematic strategy be setup with strict adherence, mobilization for social re-orientation, Anti-corruption movement launched and monitored. According to Lawal and Oladunjoye (2010), corruption makes manpower development and capacity-building sluggish as the chairmen are not thinking of the need to train and retrain staff but to embezzle funds for selfish purposes.

IV. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion this study maintains that Mindset is the ultimate in service delivery, without the right orientation poor service delivery will continue to affect the productivity of the public service organizations. The overall aim of effective service delivery is to improve customer's demands and needs, hence to create customer value, service providers must ensure that the service they offer to their customers is of high quality.

Consequently, the following recommendations are put forward for effective service delivery;

Strengthening the Mindset of Employees: Despite the plethora of legislations towards improving the Nigerian

society or its working environment, if arresting some of the corrupt mindset of many in the country is not keyed into, it could be fruitless exercises. When a mindset is corrupt, nothing positive comes out of it. Corruption has remained widespread pervasive, because of the failure to make full effect or adequate use of our National Orientation Agency, that is where the government should channel its efforts in a drive to make the society work. Hire and train professionals with the right mindset. However, as a government or an employing body, having a newly employed that does not possess the right mindset to strengthen service delivery, that is where training of that mind becomes important.

Hence, continuous training, evaluating, and checking on the mindset of employees is crucial, because, there are some that may fall off pace if not continuously and properly monitored. One of the reasons for prioritizing the mindset of service renderers is because, every day, a service employee has to deal with some delicate consumer complaint's/inquiries/demands, as such, and carefully trained minds are better equipped in handling their issues. A welltrained front line employee must be ready to face the customer as they constitute both the educated and uneducated. One of the qualities of a well-trained mind is the ability to be patient and acting in a professional manner. Thus, a proper training will prepare them for the enormous task of dealing with people that have different ways of understanding. This is where working as a service delivery agent or employee becomes delicate.

➤ *Strictly Monitor The Performances of Employees:*

A truly built mindset knows no sentiment or biasness. Being in charge of enforcement or evaluating body, monitoring the performance of subordinate. There should be a true and honest platform where customers are encouraged to detail their experiences with public or private employees, with strict penalty/punishment devoid of sentiments, tribalism meted on culprits. As a government establishment or a private employing body, establishing a complaint system which will suitably enable customers to raise their concerns should be paramount. This adversely helps in gaining an insight on the experiences subordinates or employees leave with customers. It also aids in knowing where and what calls for improvement. This medium also adds to the legitimacy of a government when consumers/masses are satisfied with government services, it

makes them feel that they are being valued by the government. It helps private employing bodies to have this special connect with their customers and know how right to treat them.

➤ *Practice Active Listening and Learn To Empathize With Customers:-*

Most public establishments in Nigeria are highly guilty of this, due to the lack of good mindset in services delivery. Behind every consumer complaint is a genuine plea for remedy to an anticipated or real problem. That person wants to be heard, understood and attended to. Empathy is an ability to understand how someone feels when coming for a solution or suggestion. Having no sense of empathy with people becomes difficult to get them understood, let alone attending to their complaints or worries. This skill can be learnt by practicing everyday with an immediate environment. Active listening affords the opportunity to learn from some of the complaints brought by others, learning reorganizes the brain. By being a good listener, provides not only the ability to become a truly exceptional service deliverer, there will be improvements in relating with people and how receptive they will be when being approached for a remedy. Strive to be on same wave length before leaving a complainant or a service seeker.

➤ *Enhanced Access To Data Information.*

Public or private service delivery enables government, private organizations to synergize with expectant customers so that effectiveness of services delivered can be efficiently assessed. One of the problems endangering good service delivery is that Nigeria does not have the right data. The country lacks the right organization or access to data to understand ways in which systems are run. No standard measure as compared to other developed nations to knowing when services are getting better or worse, so as to easily identify culprits of inadequate service delivery. Proper data usage and evaluation enables a country to easily measure its standing, its improvement or falling apart. This may suggest that ways of measuring effective service delivery is poor. Nigeria needs improvements to service information system, a regular and sustained population and workforce-based surveys, a functioning statistics unit that takes into proper account of any form of registration of employees of the public or private workforce. There is the need to strengthen

the use of evidence based ways of apprehending public or private service defaulters with strict penalties.

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